

Systematic Literature Review: The Influence Culture Organization and Motivation Work against Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Nearumi Raudha¹, Erlyta Noviana², Syukriy Abdullah³

^{1,2,3} Faculty of Economics and Business, Syiah Kuala University, Banda Aceh, Indonesia.

ABSTRACT: Overview literature systematic this aim for now influence culture organization, and motivation Work towards organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Writing method review literature systematic. This is with sourced library search method from online media such as Google Scholar, Mendeley and Academy Media other. Review results literature systematic This are 1) Culture Organization influential positive on OCB, esp with support Organization Learning and Commitment Organization and Culture Organization No influential direct significant on OCB, but influence through Motivation Work. 2) Motivation Work influential positive to OCB, especially motivation intrinsic, related direct with OCB.

KEYWORDS: Culture Organization, Motivation Work, Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

INTRODUCTION

Source Power man play very important role in reach objective organization, besides source other resources possessed by the organization. A successful company need employees who exceed their formal duties and are willing do more than expected (Steinmann et al., 2018). Flexibility is very important in environment dynamic work moment this, where is the employee the more Work in team. Organization look for willing individual do tasks that don't in a way explicit determined in description work they. Behavior employee that happened in a way voluntary, sincere, and cheerful without company must command and control good service called as Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) (Novitasari, 2020).

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is term for employee who placed mark more about the work they do carry and add mark for organization (Bergeron et al., 2011). Increase employee OCB critical For organization, therefore That important For understand what causes or increase OCB behavior. Internal characteristics such as commitment, satisfaction, competence, positivism, etc. are the two most important aspects that cause development OCB behavior. Temporary variable like method management, leadership, and culture company originate from personnel outside (external) (Navis et al., 2020; Widarko & Anwarodin, 2022; Shahab et al., 2018). Will employee For behave against OCB no can separated from factor culture organization (Widarko & Anwarodin, 2022). OCB is part unique from performance someone on the spot Work. The company is growing moment personnel willing do more from task main them, like work together, with each other support, provide advice, involvement active, giving service addition to consumer service, and use time Work they in a way effective. OCB refers to behavior prosocial or activity extracurriculars that go beyond description specified function in organization or company (Tefera & Hunsaker, 2020).

Importance foster OCB in place Work No can separated from desire employee for increase organization they. Commitment tall cause worker care about fate organization and business For guide organization to more direction OK, because That commitment tall influence employee For involved in OCB activities. Employees who own commitment to organization will guard Name Good institutions, care about fate institution, proud with institutions, bound emotional, and work with will and drive Alone so that will influence OCB (Sandakila & Satrya, 2020).

Culture organization refers to all beliefs, feelings, behavior, and symbols that characterize A organization (Lunenburg & Ornstein, 2011). Apart from considering factor culture organization, the behavior that leads to OCB is not can separated from attachment organizational employee to organization, because in the end surpassing performance what it should be in a way massively determined by strength attachment organization (Tefera & Hunsaker, 2020). Increase involvement employee need culture organizations that can influence OCB and commitment organizational in a way positive in the organization. Values organization (culture organization) and involvement employee own effect significant towards OCB (Aboramadan & Dahleez, 2020).

PT Baja Mulia Industrindo is company manufacturing engaged in the field casting metal. This company serve making product iron and steel, such as: machine spare parts, pipe fitting spare parts, manhole covers and frames, and other services production goods with

composition certain. The role of employees in the company must noticed quality it works, just like us know For increase productivity products at PT Baja Mulia Industrindo This needed power work that has characteristic volunteer or Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). Employees at PT Baja Mulia Industrindo in help colleague moderate work experience difficulties at work Still not enough maximum so that causes the production process will need long time. That matter show that PT Baja Mulia Industrindo need good cooperation between employee in finish the work is in line with the company's expectations .

Phenomenon show that low satisfaction Work employee caused by the work considered not enough interesting and monotonous, lack of challenges, opportunities limited achievements, assessed compensation No comparable, and lack promotion based on performance. Phenomenon This impact on performance low employees. Low implementation of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) also influences this satisfaction and performance employee because lack of cooperation, support, compliance with tasks, search solutions and support to objective organization between employee.

Lack of competence employees also become factor in low satisfaction and performance, visible from lack of knowledge, skills, experience that can be reliable, and lack thereof attitude professional in operate task. Apart from that, it's low culture visible organization from inability employee develop culture innovative , lack of concern for the rules organization , lack of Spirit working optimally, and lacking formation a solid team also contributed to the low satisfaction and performance employee. Therefore that's necessary strengthened OCB implementation, improvement competence employees , and formation culture positive organization For increase satisfaction and performance employee.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Organizational Citizenship Behavior is behavior that contributes to improvement context social and psychological support performance employee . OCB includes action voluntary at the level individuals who do not recognized and formally rewarded organization (Kaur & Randhawa, 2021). OCB does not depending on the system award organization but behavior volunteerism shown by willing employees Work For interest organization (Leephaijaroen, 2016). OCB has two dimensions basic (altruism), Altruism is behavior help directed at the individual certain . When individuals own problem, need help, altruistic person Work extra For help them (Jahangir et al., 2004). Deep OCB company involve a number of behavior, incl helping others, volunteering for tasks addition, and comply rules and procedures in place work (Widarko & Brotosuharto , 2022). OCB as element important in add mark for organization in company about performance, achievement objective organization when employee behave volunteer outside work they For lift price self organization (Alsheikh, 2020).

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) often defined as behavior / attitude excess workers requirements under which their formal role is No in a way direct visible and recognized by the system compensation / rewards official / standard , which can facilitate function organization (Guan & Frenkel, 2019). Citizenship company involve a number of behavior , incl helping others, volunteering take task additional , and obedient to rules and procedures in place Work . Tremblay & Simard (2018) define behavior citizenship organization as behavior free individual, no in a way direct or explicit related with rewards , and can increase function effective organization . They also take notes that *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* (OCB) is explanation alternative For performance. Organ stated that basic enough No support definition This that " role worker " someone relies on expectations and communication with sender . Based on results research, problems behavior citizenship organization has researched by many expert Because behavior This considered very important /vital for function administrative.

One of researcher, Luu (2020), with results his research, states that organization depends on contributions working employees goes beyond what the task requires For works in a way effective. Next, only A little studies theoretical study connection between factors introduction , that is behavior citizenship organization, and performance employee . According to opinion of Kanat-Maymon et al. (2018), there are two OCB divisions, namely:

1. OCB-O is giving behavior benefit for organization in a way general. As example, presence on site Work exceed established norms and adhere to informal rules (no written) for guard regularity.
2. OCB-I is behavior that is direct contribute to the organization, for example help absent colleagues from work and deliver attention more to employee other . Second OCB categories are very useful behavior for organization , though No required in a way normative Because No explained in a way official in work. Therefore that, behavior the called as behavior extra role. Temporary that, Tremblay & Simard (2018) suggest that altruism, politeness, maker peace /

maintenance peace, and guide cheered including in OCB-I category, temporary seriousness, citizenship, and sportsmanship is at in OCB-O category. Assumption This possible We show that people are power oriented Possible own monitoring more self tall. Important thing. Employee will learn and respond with fast. Employee always strength oriented For count opportunity with behavior them, then struggling to organization " if That help they achieve their agenda.

Culture Organization

Culture organization is system mark together in a the organization that is becoming reference For How employee operate activity To use reach objective or ambition organization. Usually stated in vision, mission and goals organization. Culture organization developed from a collection of norms, values, beliefs, hopes, assumptions and philosophies of its members. Therefore That does not surprising If culture the Then seen with clear in behavior individual and group.

According to Regulation of the Minister of Empowerment State Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform Number 39/2012 concerning Guidelines Coaching Culture Work, culture organizations also become base practice inside organization, incl How member organization finish work and interact One each other. Culture organization develop become mechanism control, influence How employee interact with holder outside interests organization. Change in culture company influence change behavior employees inside organization. Change in culture organization applies start from level highest down to the smallest unit in the organization. Behavior leader organization in a way massively determine success in develop and build culture company influence change behavior employees inside organization. Change in culture organization applies start from level highest down to the smallest unit in the organization. Behavior leader organization in a way massively determine success in develop and build culture company.

Motivation Work

Motivation related with efforts made somebody in reach something objective . Motivation tightly connection with satisfaction work and performance employee. According to (Hu et al., 2022), motivation This important for manager because, according to definition, manager must Work with other people. Manager must understand behavior certain people to influence them to work in accordance with need organization. Motivation is Skills For direct employees to want Work with success For reach desire employees and goals organization.

Motivation is strength hidden causes or push We For behave or Act with method certain. Sometimes motivation nature instinctive (influenced by instinct), and sometimes appear from decision rational (Padave et al., 2021). Motivation is condition psychology that arises from interaction between need employees and factors external influences behavior employees (Yang et al., 2021). Motivation is mental state and attitude man who gives energy, drive activity, and directing behavior going to fulfillment need.

Study Previous

Table 1. Research Previous

No	Title Researcher Year	Research purposes	Variable Research & Research methods	Research result
1	Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Work Performance: Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) as Mediating Variable. Widarko & Anwarodin, (2022)	The purpose of study This is analyze influence motivation work, culture organization, Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) towards performance civil servants (ASN).	Variable depdent : - Performance of Civil Servants (PNS) Variable Independent : - Motivation Work - Culture Organization Variables : - Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)	Research result show that - motivation Work own impact positive directly on OCB, especially on employees with motivation intrinsic high showing attitude Work more and more answer . - culture organization No own influence directly to OCB.

	<p>Golden Ratio of Human Resource Management, Vol.2, Issue. 2 (2022)</p>		<p>Research methods used in studies This is method survey . Research sample consists of 236 ASN respondents from Regency Blitar , East Java Province , Indonesia, was selected use stratified proportional random sampling method .</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Motivation work is also proven own impact positive directly on ASN performance, while OCB directly direct influence performance. Although Thus, role deep OCB mediation connection between culture organization and performance No fully strong, showing exists other factors that can influence connection the. - The implication is management can increase effectiveness organization with pay attention and take advantage combination variable like motivation work , culture organization , OCB, and performance .
<p>2</p>	<p>Organizational Culture and Organizational Citizenship Behavior: The Mediating Role of Learning Organizations and Organizational Commitment.</p> <p>Siswadi et al., (2023)</p> <p>Journal of Business and Management Research Volume 16, No. 1, February 2023</p>	<p>Study This aim For know how the Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) Model is based Culture Organization mediated by the Organization Learning and Commitment Organization.</p>	<p>Variable dependent :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) <p>Variable independent :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Culture organization <p>Variable Mediating :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learning organization - Commitment organization <p>Research methods used in studies This is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), with approach analytical using the Maximum Likelihood Estimate (MLE) estimation model . size sample For study This is 200 lecturers remains at a private university in North</p>	<p>Research result show that :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Culture Organization, Organization Learning , and Commitment Organization own influence significant positive on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). - Culture Organizations and Organizations Learning own influence significant positive to Commitment Organization . - Organization Learning in a way positive mediate influence Culture Organization towards Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), and - Commitment Organization mediate influence Culture Organization on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB).

			Sumatra. Data analysis method used is Structural Equation Modeling.	
3	<p>How to Enhance an Employee's Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) as a Corporate Strategy.</p> <p>Eungoo & Hwang, (2023)</p> <p>Journal of Industrial Distribution & Business Vol 14 No 1 (2023)</p>	<p>Study This aim For explore method improve Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) for company private with objective increase performance employee . With implemented OCB , the company No need worry about employee involved in action dangerous or counterproductive . More coordination Good will give benefit for Skills employees and performance whole company .</p>	<p>Variable Dependents :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), <p>Variable Independent :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Management Human Resources (HR) - Management Corporate Strategic <p>method study No served in a way detailed , some element like form data extraction and investigation on duplication show that study This Possible involve qualitative data analysis or combined between analysis Qualitative and quantitative .</p>	<p>There are four solution For increase employee OCB for HR practitioner :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create Environment that Supports Constructive OCB , - Push Behavior Productive on the Spot Work and Give Award with Appropriate , - Integrate Company Citizenship to in Performance evaluation , - Training For Using OCB and Education about The benefits . <p>Study This conclude with firm that OCB should be driven , and entrepreneur as well as employee should collaborate in effort For increase enthusiasm and productivity . As results direct from effort them , the company they enjoy enhancement income while experience subtraction overhead costs .</p>
4	<p>The Effect of Organizational Citizens' Behavior (OCB), Competence, and Organizational Culture on Performance: Employee Satisfaction as Mediating Variable.</p> <p>Hatidja et al., (2022)</p>	<p>Study This is For analyze the influence of Organizational Citizens' Behavior (OCB), competence , and culture organization to satisfaction Work employees , analyze influence behavior citizenship organization , competence , and culture organization to performance employees , analyze satisfaction Work to performance employees , and analyze influence behavior citizenship organization , competence , and culture organization to performance through</p>	<p>Variable dependent :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Employee performance <p>Independent variable :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organizational Citizens' Behavior (OCB), - competence , - Culture organization <p>Variable Mediation :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Satisfaction Employee <p>method data collection uses observation , questionnaires , interviews , and</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - behavior citizenship organization own influence negative and not significant to satisfaction Work employee . This matter caused by difficulties employee in apply indicators behavior citizenship organization, which resulted lack of characteristic behavior comparative and innovative in handle work they . Temporary that's the cause behavior citizenship organization No own influence significant to satisfaction work, because lack of orientation and

	<p>International Journal Of Artificial Intelligence Research ISSN: 2579-7298 Vol 6, No 1.2, 2022</p>	<p>satisfaction Work employee .</p>	<p>documentation . Research sites carried out at Bank Mandiri (Persero) Tbk in Makassar City. Research sample This were 265 respondents selected with use Slovin's formula . Data analysis techniques used in explain phenomenon in study This is technique analysis statistics descriptive and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis .</p>	<p>prospects satisfying work in develop behavior nice work .</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Behavior member organizations also have influence negative and not significant to performance employees , because all indicator No support ability employee in develop behavior they For reach results optimal work . More further , behavior member organization own influence negative and not significant to performance through satisfaction Work employee . This matter caused by difficulties employee in apply indicator variables , esp Because demands services performed by employees must in accordance with applicable systems , procedures , policies and provisions in organization , so difficult For develop behavior in accordance with desires and interests customer .
<p>5</p>	<p>The Impact of Spiritual Leadership and Motivational Leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Religious Performance: Evidence from Indonesian Islamic Schools. Muharom, (2023)</p>	<p>Research purposes This is For explore influence Behavior Citizenship Organization (OCB), spiritual leadership , and spiritual motivation towards performance religion in Integrated Islamic Kindergartens and Elementary Schools in Indonesia. Study this is also purposeful For give understanding about interaction complex between variables the in context Islamic education .</p>	<p>Variable Dependents :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) - Religious Performance <p>Variable Independent :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Leadership and Leadership Motivation <p>With approach quantitative through survey and analysis track use multiple linear regression</p>	<p>The results of data analysis show that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - motivation and spiritual leadership have influence significant towards OCB. - motivation and spiritual leadership as well significant influence performance religious . - Analysis This show that enhancement motivation and spiritual leadership encourage OCB and produce results performance more

	Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Yönetimi Educational Administration : Theory and Practice 2023			religious Good in period long . - By more extensive , research This give valuable insight for Islamic schools in Indonesia for increase performance religious teachers and staff .
6	Influence Work , and Perceived Supervisor Support for Organizational Citizenship Behavior with Satisfaction Work As Mediator . Sari & Kurniawan, (2023) Journal Management and Science, 8(1), 2023: 541-550	Study This aim For know influence involvement work , and perceived supervisor support towards organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) with decision Work as variable mediation .	Variable dependent : - Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). Variable independent : - Involvement Work - Perceived supervisor support. - Variable mediation : - Satisfaction Work. Study This is study quantitative with use population all employee of PT Baja Mulia Industrindo Klaten . Data collection census , with total of 50 respondents using a questionnaire survey . Data analysis using analysis inferential with the statistical program used is Smart PLS 3.	Research result show that - involvement Work influential negative No significant towards OCB, - satisfaction Work influential positive No significant towards OCB, - perceived supervisor support has an influence positive No significant to satisfaction Work , - involvement Work influential positive significant to satisfaction Work , - perceived supervisor support has an influence positive significant towards OCB, - satisfaction Work capable mediate connection between involvement Work towards OCB, - satisfaction Work capable mediate connection between perceived supervisor support and OCB.
7	Impact of Psychological Contract Violation on Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Intention to Quit and Commitment. Ullah et al., (2022)	The purpose of article This is For analyze connection violation contract psychological with Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), intentions For quit, and commit organization.	Variable dependent : - Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) - Intention For stop - Commitment Organizational Variable independent : - Violation Contract Psychological	Violation contract nature emotional and not nature written, as well violation sustainable to contract psychological can cause intention For stop , decline behavior citizenship organization (OCB), and low commitment . All organization No can overcome results negative this is in place Work. Findings our results are supportive hypothesis research, and we conclude that

MDRI (Management Development & Research Innovation) Vol. 1, Issue. 1, Received: 21 NOV 2022		Survey method used through primary data collection with approach piece latitude of 349 employees banking in Pakistan. Taking sample use non- probability convenience sampling method.	contract psychological own significant influence on behavior citizenship organization , intention For quit , and commit .
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Methodology Study

Writing method article scientific This is with method qualitative and research library (library research). Review theory and relationships or influence between variable from books and journals Good offline in the library and online sourced from Mendeley, Google Scholar, and other online media .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Influence Culture Organization on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

In development culture organization, almost always guaranteed that the leaders organization become agent change. As agent change one contribution expected significance is Act as role model. In life everyday, someone No can separated from the environment. Environment that will too form personality somebody. For personality That leads to attitudes and behavior positive, of course must supported by recognized norms truth and obey it as guide in Act. Man or somebody in life organizational try define and shape something that can accommodate interest all party so that in operate activity they do not contradictory with various attitudes and behavior. What is meant is is culture in which individuals being, like values, beliefs, assumptions, expectations, etc. Culture bureaucratic shared become a number of part, with clear difference between rights and obligations.

Culture innovative always Act in a way creative, results oriented, and able overcome challenges in the world of work. Supportive culture describe form priority cooperation interest together. According to (Taghipour & Dejban , 2013); (Niar , 2022; Saraswati, 2022), culture can defined as knowledge gained For interpret experience and produce behavior social . Culture organization are the guiding norms and values behavior member company. Every member will behave in accordance with prevailing culture For accepted by the environment (Azizah et al., 2022; Hasrat & Rosyadah, 2021; Mahmoud et al., 2016; Marpaung et al., 2021). Culture organization No own the same effect on formation behavior every member organization. There is a strong culture, and there is weak culture. If culture the in a way firm held by some big member organized and guided in every action, then culture the said strong. Employee more committed , and vice versa , depending on some factors, such as capacity organization , duration organization standing, changing member executive , and origin culture (Abdelzاهر et al., 2017; Taghipour & Dejban , 2013; Tsai et al., 2007). So culture organization related with values, habits, ways work, ceremonies, and traditions , accepted by members organization as something system meaning together, as characteristics special (identity) that differentiates they from element organization other. System meaning together This is set always part found when observed. In observation, this is set features always found in A organization and usual used as the norm is not written However held and implemented every day. Study conducted by Siswadi et al. (2023) show that Culture Organization own influence positive towards OCB, esp when supported by the Organization Learning and Commitment Organization. However, other research such as that conducted by Widarko & Anwarodin (2022) shows that Culture Organization No own influence significant direct towards OCB, however can influence OCB through Motivation Work.

Influence Motivation Work on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Schwepker & Dimitriou (2021) propose explanation as existing encouragement in somebody For behave To use reach objective certain with endeavor create condition certain in himself so that his behavior directed to desired goal . Motivation is strength the impetus that will realize behavior for reach objective satisfaction self. Motivation formed from attitude a employee in face situation Work . Motivation is desire in self someone who causes that person in action. Normal people fight for something objective. So, motivation is impulse controlled by a plan and rarely appear so just . Words like needs, desires, drives, and goals everything such as the motives from which the phrase “ motivation ” originates (Gilson et al., 2005).

According to Tian et al. (2016), motivation is Skills in direct employees and organizations to work with success so that desire employees and goals organization can achieved in a way simultaneously . Herzberg's theory of motivation, or “hygienic,” assumes that One group factors , namely motivators, provide level high motivation . Group other from factor hygienic, or factor maintenance yes cause dissatisfaction Work . Gawel (1997) sees it as something complexity factors-attitudes-effects that have been done on one research unit , ie as complexity factor-attitude-effect (FA-E). Result of a number of study show that Motivation Work own positive influence towards OCB. Widarko & Anwarodin (2022) found that motivation work, esp motivation intrinsic, related direct with OCB. Another study conducted by Muharom (2023) also shows this that motivation work and spiritual leadership contribute positive towards OCB.

CONCLUSION

Based on review References to a number of study related, yes concluded that Culture Organization and Motivation Work own significant role in forming Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in the environment Work. Research by Siswadi et al. (2023) show that Culture Organization can influential positive towards OCB, esp when supported by the Organization Learning and Commitment Organization. However, findings from Widarko & Anwarodin (2022) stated that Culture Organization No own influence significant direct towards OCB, but rather through its influence to Motivation Work .

Apart from that, Motivation Work , especially motivation intrinsic , discovered relate direct with deep OCB the same study by Widarko & Anwarodin (2022). The results of another research by Muharom (2023) added that motivation work and spiritual leadership also contribute positive towards OCB. OCB also plays role important as a mediator between Culture Organization, Motivation Work, and performance employees, as shown in study Widarko & Anwarodin (2022).

By overall, review References This describe that Culture Organization and Motivation Work own significant role in form OCB in various context organization . Researches this also shows that OCB can works as mediation between factors the with performance employee. The implication is management organization can increase performance and productivity employee with pay attention and manage Culture Supporting organizations, as well increase Motivation Work through relevant strategies. With So , understanding deep about connection between Culture Organization , Motivation Work , and OCB can give valuable insight for managers and leaders organization in designing improvement - oriented policies and strategies performance and satisfaction employee.

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